

OPTIMIZATION OF THE COST PRIORITY NUMBER (CPN) METHODOLOGY TO THE NEEDS OF A LARGE O&M OPERATOR

G. Oviedo Hernández^{1*}, S. Lindig², D. Moser² and P. V. Chiantore¹

¹BayWa r.e. Operation Services S.r.l., Via di Settebagni 390, 00139 Rome, Italy

²Institute for Renewable Energy, EURAC Research, Viale Druso 1, 39100 Bolzano, Italy

*Phone: +39 346 1175 310; E-mail: guillermo.hernandez@baywa-re.it

ABSTRACT: A methodology capable to assess the economic impact of failures in PV projects was one of the main outcomes of the H2020 project Solar Bankability. It was a first attempt to derive a cost-based FMEA (Failure Mode and Effect Analysis) methodology for the PV sector using the metric CPN (Cost Priority Number) instead of the RPN (Risk Priority Number) as typically used in classical FMEA. It was originally applied by developing theoretical scenarios to calculate extreme values for the CPN metric, expressed in Euros/kW_p/year. In this study, the methodology has been updated and adapted to the needs of a large O&M operator and applied manually to monitoring data and maintenance tickets of a fielded utility-scale PV plant. The main objective was to identify the adjustments needed to take the implementation of the methodology a step further towards a fully automatized approach. Additionally, the most relevant O&M contractor Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as *detect*, *response* and *repair times*, which are the cornerstone of the proposed economic analysis, were revisited and reformulated. Finally, the methodology was further improved by introducing more accurate calculations for Performance Ratio (PR), plant degradation and energy losses.

Keywords: large grid-connected PV systems, O&M, technical risks, economic analysis, bankability

1 INTRODUCTION

The Cost Priority Number (CPN) methodology was developed in the Solar Bankability project [1] back in 2017, in which the risk assessment connected to investments in PV projects was studied. The methodology helps to identify and classify the technical risks and their economic impact by assigning a cost metric that supports preventive and corrective measures, which then would lower the impact of failures on the availability and performance of a PV plant. This methodology is an implementation of a cost-based Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) to the PV sector and defines an estimation of the economic losses due to system downtime and the substitution/repair of components, named CPN (Cost Priority Number), expressed in €/kW_p/year. It was originally developed by creating theoretical scenarios which took into account all phases of a PV plant life cycle (from product testing to decommissioning).

The work in this paper is only focused on the operation and maintenance (O&M) phase which is by far the longest one in the life cycle of a PV plant (20-25 years). Real monitoring data were used and information was extracted from maintenance tickets in order to improve the accuracy of the methodology by stepping away from theoretical assumptions. This approach will help to further standardize the methodology and to acquire more applicable results for the industry. In further future studies, the work will be expanded to a portfolio of 127 PV plants, which combine 150 MW of installed power, in order to collect a statistically relevant distribution in terms of occurrence and impact of technical risks.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1. Case study

This paper was focused on a utility-scale PV plant in operation in central Italy since 2013 (see Table I).

A total of 191 maintenance tickets were analysed manually, corresponding to all planned and corrective activities carried out in the year 2018. Since 2015 the plant is under management of BayWa r.e., a full-fledged O&M

contractor. Time-series of monitoring data are available since November 2016, including on-site irradiance (pyranometer measurements) and power (inverter measurements) in high resolution (5-min granularity).

A detailed metadata table was created containing all relevant parameter, mapping all components of the plant whose failure could cause a power loss. This metadata table was populated, using as source, the available as-built documentation, the O&M contract and some other documents related to Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditures (OPEX).

Table I: Summary of PV plant metadata

Installation type	Ground-mounted fixed tilt
Installed capacity	9,019.53 kW _p
Country	Italy
Commissioning date	25/08/2013
Start monitoring date	08/11/2016
Feed in tariff	0.119 €/kWh
Number of modules	69,381
Module nominal power	130 W _p
Number of inverters	17
Inverter nominal power	500 kW

2.2 Technical risks during operation

In an effort to further promote a standard nomenclature for technical risks in the PV sector, this work was performed in line with the structure and wording defined by the Solar Bankability project in the so-called Technical Risk Matrix, which is publicly available [2]. Only the technical risks corresponding to the O&M phase were taken into account.

2.3 O&M contractor KPIs

After reviewing the most updated Key Performance Indicator (KPI) definitions in the *Operation & Maintenance Best Practices Guidelines* published by the industry association SolarPower Europe [3], they were adapted for being applicable to the CPN methodology. The revised KPIs are as following, calculated with the parameters defined in Table II:

Table II: Parameters to calculate the O&M contractor KPIs, extracted from the monitoring and ticketing system

Failure time	Time when a failure occurs, e.g. performance deviation beyond allowed threshold or inverter error code generated. An alarm is triggered.
Acknowledgment time	Time when the fault is acknowledged by the O&M Contractor. A maintenance ticket is opened.
Intervention time	Time when the technician arrives on-site with all the tools and spare parts needed to fix the problem.
Repair switch-off time	Time when an upper-level component of the plant has to be powered off in order to fix a problem.
Repair switch-on time	Time when an upper-level component of the plant is re-established after being powered off to fix the problem.
Resolution time	Time when the fault is fixed and acknowledged by the O&M Contractor's control room personnel. The maintenance ticket is closed.

- a) *Detection time*: time that it takes to detect the occurrence of a fault. With a good monitoring system this time should be zero or just a few minutes. For plants without monitoring, this could take weeks or months, until the failure is detected during the next scheduled maintenance intervention. It is calculated as follows:

$$t_{detection} [h] = \text{acknowledgement time} - \text{failure time} \quad (1)$$

- b) *Response time*: time that it takes to organise the repair or substitution. It might include one or several of the following activities: trouble shooting process, remote repair, dispatching of a technician to the field; if a substitution of a component is needed, a spare parts management procedure would be triggered (and in the worst case scenario, the management of acquisition of the spare parts directly from the manufacturer, including the transport to the site). Therefore, this time is highly dependent on the availability of spare parts. It is calculated as follows:

$$t_{response} [h] = \text{intervention time} - \text{acknowledgement time} \quad (2)$$

- c) *Repair time*: time that it takes the technician(s) to fix the problem. After the repair or substitution is completed, and the PV plant is restored to normal operating conditions, the intervention should be validated by the O&M contractor's control room personnel. It is calculated as follows:

$$t_{repair} [h] = \text{resolution time} - \text{intervention time} \quad (3)$$

- d) *Shutdown time*: time in which an upper-level component of the plant has to be turned off in order to fix the problem (e.g. for safety reasons, a combiner box needs to be switched off to replace a module). It is part of the *repair time*, calculated as follows:

$$t_{shutdown} [h] = \frac{\text{repair switch-off time} - \text{repair switch-on time}}{\text{repair switch-on time}} \quad (4)$$

2.4 Calculation of the CPN metric

In the CPN methodology only failures that have an economic impact are taken into account and are split into two categories:

- a) Economic impact due to downtime (C_{down}):
- Failures that cause downtime or power loss
 - Considers the time from failure to repair/substitution
 - Special attention to failures at component level which might affect other components (e.g. a module failure might bring down the whole string)
- b) Economic impact due to repair (C_{fix}):
- Cost of detection to account for various techniques

(visual inspection, Infrared (IR) imagery for thermal anomalies, current-voltage (I-V) curve tracing for power deviations, electroluminescence (EL) for cracked cells, etc.)

- Cost of transportation of a component
- Cost of labour (linked to repair time)
- Cost of repair/substitution of a component

The CPN metric, if applied to an entire year of O&M activities, is defined as follows:

$$\text{CPN} [\text{€}/\text{kW}_p/\text{year}] = C_{down} + C_{fix} \quad (5)$$

2.4.1 Calculation of the costs due to downtime

This calculation is done for each specific failure found in the period analysed. The first step is to calculate the PR when a specific failure occurs, using as starting point the annual average PR calculated with the first available complete year of monitoring data.

$$PR_{fail} [\%] = \frac{PR_{start_{monitoring}} - PLR \cdot (\text{year}_{fail} - \text{year}_{start_{monitoring}})}{PLR} \quad (6)$$

The Performance Loss Rate (PLR) is calculated using the method *seasonal-trend decomposition using LOESS* (STL), which was selected based on a comparative study of available algorithms [4]. This method decomposes a time-series into its subparts and extracts a long-term trend of PR values. This trend is then subject to linear regression and the PLR is given in percentage per year. The PR as well as the PLR is calculated according to [5].

The next steps are the calculation of the O&M contractor KPIs defined in section 2.3 and the *Specific Yield Loss* (Y_{loss}), which is the energy per kW_p that the plant would have produced if unaffected by the failure. It is calculated separately for the four intervals of interest (*detection time*, *response time*, *repair time* and *shutdown time*):

$$Y_{loss} [\text{kWh}/\text{kW}_p] = H_{loss} \cdot PR_{fail} \quad (7)$$

H_{loss} is the irradiation incident on the PV plant during the failure. The irradiation data is taken from the monitoring system (on-site irradiance sensor data) or from a satellite-based source when ground measurements are not available or reliable. Then, the energy loss is calculated, normalized by the total number of components affected by a specific failure. It is calculated separately for the four intervals of interest (*detection time*, *response time*, *repair time* and *shutdown time*):

$$E_{loss_detection} = Y_{loss_detection} \cdot P_0 \cdot \left(\frac{n_{fail}}{n_{total}}\right) \cdot CPL \cdot M_1 \quad (8)$$

$$E_{loss_response} = Y_{loss_response} \cdot P_0 \cdot \left(\frac{n_{fail}}{n_{total}}\right) \cdot CPL \cdot M_1 \quad (9)$$

$$E_{loss_repair} = (Y_{loss_repair} - Y_{loss_shutdown}) \cdot P_0 \cdot \left(\frac{n_{fail}}{n_{total}}\right) \cdot CPL \cdot M_1 \quad (10)$$

$$E_{loss_shutdown} = Y_{loss_shutdown} \cdot P_0 \cdot \left(\frac{n_{fail}}{n_{total}}\right) \cdot M_2 \quad (11)$$

The total energy loss is the sum of the values above:

$$E_{loss_TOTAL} [\text{kWh}] = E_{loss_detection} + E_{loss_response} + E_{loss_repair} + E_{loss_shutdown} \quad (12)$$

See Table III for a detailed explanation of each parameter. *Component Power Loss* (CPL) corresponds to the PL parameter in the original methodology [1], but it was renamed for the sake of clarity, because it defines the power loss just for the affected component and not for the entire plant. For example, a CPL = 50% means that this component is working at half of its capacity. Ideally, it can be calculated from the monitoring data. If not, refer to Table V in [1] for reasonable assumed values.

M_1 is a multiplier to consider failures that cause problems at higher component level during *detection*, *response* and *repair times* (excluding shutdown). For example, if one module takes down the whole string (e.g. caused by theft) and the string has 13 modules, then M_1 equals 13. M_2 is a multiplier to consider failures that cause problems at higher component level only during *shutdown time*. For example, if an entire combiner box with 10 strings has to be switched off to replace only one broken module and each string has 13 modules, then M_2

equals 10 x 13.

Finally, C_{down} is calculated as follows:

$$C_{down} [\text{€/kW}_p/\text{year}] = \frac{E_{loss_TOTAL} \cdot FIT}{P_0} \quad (13)$$

For the calculation of the costs due to downtime, it is very important to consider the missing income related to the sale of electricity, defined by the feed in tariff (FIT), the power-purchasing agreement (PPA) or the missing savings generated by PV plants installed on roofs/facades defined as retail cost of electricity (RCE). For this case study, the FIT was used.

2.4.2. Calculation of costs due to repair

The cost of labour due to each specific failure was calculated using the *repair time* as defined previously, the number of technicians deployed n_{ST} and the internal cost per hour C_{ST} :

$$C_{labour} [\text{€}] = t_{repair} \cdot n_{ST} \cdot C_{ST} \quad (14)$$

C_{fix} is calculated with some additional parameters defined in Table IV:

$$C_{fix} [\text{€/kW}_p/\text{year}] = \frac{(C_{detect} + C_{repair} + C_{transp} + C_{labour}) \cdot n_{fail}}{P_0} \quad (15)$$

Table III: Parameter definition for the calculation of the CPN

PR_{fail}	Performance Ratio when failure occurs [%]	n_{fail}	Number of components affected
$PR_{start_monitoring}$	Annual average PR calculated with the first available complete year of monitoring data [%]	n_{total}	Total number of components
PLR	Performance Loss Rate calculated using at least two years of historical data [%/year]	CPL	Component Power Loss [%]
$year_{fail}$	Year when failure occurs	M_1	Multiplier to consider failures that cause problems at higher component level during <i>detection</i> , <i>response</i> and <i>repair times</i> (excluding <i>shutdown time</i>) [--]
$year_{start_monitoring}$	Year from which monitoring data is available	M_2	Multiplier to consider failures that cause problems at higher component level during the <i>shutdown time</i> [--]
Y_{loss}	Specific Yield Loss, energy per kW _p that the plant would have produced if unaffected by the failure [kWh/kW _p]	FIT	Feed in tariff [€/kWh]
H_{loss}	Irradiation loss, calculated as the sum of Plane of Array (POA) irradiation [kWh/m ²]	C_{labour}	Cost of labour [€]
$E_{loss_detection}$	Energy loss during detection [kWh]	t_{repair}	Repair time [h]
$E_{loss_response}$	Energy loss during response [kWh]	n_{ST}	Number of site technicians involved in the repair activity
E_{loss_repair}	Energy loss during repair [kWh]	C_{ST}	Internal cost (rate per hour) of the site technician [€/h]
$E_{loss_shutdown}$	Energy loss during shutdown [kWh] considers CPL=100%	C_{detect}	Cost of detection [€/component] To account for various techniques (visual inspection, IR for thermal anomalies, I-V curve tracing for power deviations, EL for cracked cells, etc.)
E_{loss_TOTAL}	Total energy loss [kWh]	C_{repair}	Cost of repair/substitution [€/component]
P_0	Total installed capacity of the PV plant [kW _p]	C_{transp}	Cost of transportation [€/component]

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The methodology has been applied manually to one case study, which led to important improvements, especially in terms of the structure and standardisation of the CPN table. See some examples of critical situations in Table IV, where the highest CPN number corresponds to a failure of a central inverter's subcomponent, which took 26 days to be delivered and replaced by the manufacturer, confirming thus the high dependency of *repair time* on the

availability of spare parts. In this particular case, the methodology would draw the attention of a decision maker towards spare parts management in order to mitigate this technical risk in the future.

The analysis of real maintenance tickets led to the optimization of the number and format of the input parameters. Instead of using the methodology to create scenarios based on assumptions that would cover a wide spectrum of O&M approaches, real data from a specific O&M contractor were used. Parameters such as costs of

interventions and spare parts, failure, acknowledgement, response and repair times were directly extracted from the monitoring and ticketing system.

This task proved to be very time-consuming because although the description of failure and corrective measures is common practice in the field of O&M, it is not often carried out with the sufficient level of detail to derive meaningful statistical analysis due to the lack of a standardized approach in the assignment, wording and categorization of failures.

The methodology was further improved by introducing more accurate calculations for plant degradation and PR. As presented in section 2.4.1, the PLR was calculated using STL, with which the PR was calculated for the time of failure occurrence, instead of assuming a fixed PR value for all the tickets for the whole period analysed. For the calculation of the initial PR, it

might be desirable to use as starting point the PR calculated right after the commissioning of the plant or after a certain amount of sun exposure after which initial degradation effects, usually seen in PV modules, are eliminated and a stable system operation is ensured. These data usually belong to the installation phase of the project and it might be not available for the O&M contractor who takes over the plant after 2-5 years of operation (typically a different company than the original EPC contractor). So, for consistency, we restricted this work only to data available to the O&M contractor.

The calculation of the energy loss was consequently also adapted by integrating irradiance measurements from on-site sensors into the *Specific Yield Loss* formula, avoiding therefore, the uncertainty related to statistical assumptions.

Table IV: Extract of the CPN table related to the case study

Ticket name	Detecti on time	Response time	Repair time	Total Energy Loss	C_{fix}		C_{down}		CPN
	h	h	h	kWh	€	€/kW _p	€	€/kW _p	€/kW _p /year
Inverter 3D off	0.40	0.10	1.33	423.86	50.44	0.01	46.67	0.005	0.011
Meter 1 connect error	18.20	1.00	95.55	0.00	0.00	0.00	255.00	0.028	0.028
Repair of 2 strings	0.17	0.25	0.75	239.15	28.46	0.00	86.25	0.010	0.013
Inverter 1B off	2.60	126.15	502.83	27,955.61	3,326.72	0.37	1,066.00	0.118	0.487
Inverter 1B off	1.18	0.40	0.58	76.37	9.09	0.00	20.42	0.002	0.003
Inverters cabin 3 off	8.70	16.30	0.83	4,704.45	559.83	0.06	29.17	0.003	0.065
Inverter 1B off	1.58	1.00	8.17	2,325.50	276.73	0.03	285.83	0.032	0.062
PLANT OFF	0.17	0.17	19.83	11,360.19	1,351.86	0.15	35.00	0.004	0.154

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study was carried out to better understand the CPN methodology and to evaluate its applicability in routine operations of a large O&M operator. The development of an automated and therefore, time-efficient solution for extracting key parameters from maintenance tickets is of vital importance for the implementation of the methodology at portfolio level, and thus, to gain statistical insights from a large number of PV plants. The CPN methodology, possibly applied as a relational database, could be used in the back end of software dedicated to the asset management of PV plants.

Furthermore, the development of a more sophisticated software tool for field technicians that would allow the precise and error-free recording of standardised parameters for the calculation of the O&M contractors KPIs is necessary for an efficient implementation of the methodology, which has been proven to be highly dependent on how data structured inside the ticketing system. In this study, a non-neglectable amount of interpretation and analysis was required to extract such parameters, that, if not done carefully and consistently, might jeopardize the accuracy of the CPN metric and ultimately rendering the methodology as not applicable for benchmarking.

Although state-of-the-art O&M field practices have moved away from paper format tickets and have adopted digital ticketing systems, there is still room for improvement, especially regarding the language and wording used to describe failures in the field. Enhancements are envisioned with the adoption of a more

standardised approach when human intervention is limited to choosing the category and failure type from a pre-defined selection list (in line with the nomenclature already developed by the Solar Bankability project). Such efforts have already taken off and by the time this work was written, they were under advanced development [6].

In the incoming years, as Industry 4.0 products and services start to become market-ready and deployed massively in the PV sector, investors and decision makers will benefit from a uniformed approach to reduce the perceived risks and to maximize the performance of their assets.

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under GA. No. 721452 – H2020-MSCA-ITN-2016.

6 REFERENCES

- [1] D. Moser, M. Del Buono, M. Jahn, M. Herz, M. Richter and K. De Brabandere, "Identification of Technical Risks in the PV Value Chain and Quantification of the Economic Impact on the Business Model," *Progress in Photovoltaics: Research and Applications*, vol. 25, no. 7, pp. 592-604, 2017.
- [2] Solar Bankability project, Technical Risk Matrix, www.solarbankability.org/results.html, accessed 30/08/2019
- [3] Operation & Maintenance Best Practices Guidelines v3.0, SolarPower Europe, December 2018

- [4] S. Lindig, I. Kaaya, K. Weiß, D. Moser and M. Topic, "Review of Statistical and Analytical Degradation Models for Photovoltaic Modules and Systems as Well as Related Improvements," in IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics, vol. 8, no. 6, pp. 1773-1786, Nov. 2018.
- [5] S. Lindig, P. Ingenhoven, G. Belluardo, D. Moser and M. Topic, "Evaluation of Technology-Dependent Maximum Power Point Current and Voltage Degradation in a Temperate Climate," in 35th EU PVSEC, Brussels, 2018.
- [6] Antares, PV 4.0 project, www.antares.uno/prodotto/rd/progetto-pv-4-0/, accessed 30/08/2019